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THE NATIONAL DISTINCTIVENESS OF THE KARAKALPAK VERSION OF THE DASTAN “SAYATKHAN-KHAMRA”

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In world folklore studies, along with the growing attention to identifying the unique national features of oral folk art, its historical foundations, and the artistic and aesthetic principles governing its stages of development, there has been a gradual expansion of research that highlights the mutual influence of dastan schools, the genesis, and typology of traditional dastans. As a result, theoretical ideas have been deeply substantiated, affirming that the genetic foundations of similar epic plots—widespread among peoples belonging to the same language family—are in fact connected to archaic motifs of mythological epics.

Such new scientific and theoretical concepts in epic studies have raised to a qualitatively new level the research concerning the distinctive nature of romantic-adventurous dastans, their typological features, and artistic evolution. This, in turn, provides a theoretical basis for studying the Karakalpak version of the dastan Sayatkhan-Khamra in a typological aspect.

Recent international folklore research devoted to the history of genre formation related to the epic tradition, its evolution, and classification, has demonstrated the importance of considering national peculiarities of folklore traditions when classifying folk epics by theme. The renewal of views regarding epic theory has led to the emergence of studies aimed at defining the principles of forming different versions and variants as a result of the evolutionary development of epic plots. The introduction of these new theoretical perspectives into Turkic—and particularly Karakalpak—folklore studies has made it possible to determine the dominant features inherent in the national version of romantic dastans such as Sayatkhan-Khamra, as

well as their place within the broader context of the epic creativity of the peoples of the region.

At present, consistent reforms are being implemented to further strengthen spiritual immunity, and the preservation and popularization of tangible and intangible cultural heritage has been elevated to the level of a nationwide task. In particular, the work aimed at preserving and developing the traditions of bakhshi—which had an enormous influence on the artistic thinking of our people—and the scholarly study and publication of dastans, priceless epic works that were created and refined over centuries, serves the noble purpose of educating a well-rounded young generation.

Two variants of the Karakalpak version of the dastan Sayatkhan-Khamra have been published: in 1985, the version of bakhshi Minazh Matsapayev appeared in Volume 14 of the multi-volume edition of Karakalpak folklore, and in 2011, the version of Zhuman bakhshi was published in Volume 36 of the same series. These variants have taken their rightful place among the most complete and accomplished examples of the Karakalpak versions of this dastan. A comparative analysis of the dastan with versions from other peoples was conducted based on these two variants. Through a mutual analysis of Turkic versions of the dastan, we were able to determine “the distinctive subsequent development of the epic tradition among each nation” [13, p.82].

It should be noted that there are very few scholarly opinions regarding the national versions and variants of the dastan Sayatkhan-Khamra. In particular, among Karakalpak scholars, N. Davkaraev, K. Ayimbetov, and K. Maksetov in their works provided only brief information about the dastan, its genre-specific features, artistic qualities, themes, and performers. In the article by Zh. Khoshniyazov and Yu. Baysagatov, “The Distinctive Features of the Origin and Spread of Karakalpak Lyric-Epic Dastans”, published in *The Bulletin of KKO AS RUz* [15, p.53], the authors discuss the preservation, dissemination, and performance features of lyric-epic dastans among our people, and also briefly touch upon the dastan Sayatkhan-Khamra.

Regarding the emergence and wide dissemination of romantic dastans among the Karakalpak people, numerous opinions exist, some of which contradict one another. For instance, Professor Kalli Ayimbetov, who wrote an extensive study on the performers of Karakalpak folk dastans — zhyrau and bakhshi — stated that bakhshi among the Karakalpaks appeared much later than zhyrau, after the latter migrated and settled in the Khorezm region [1, p.126].

According to the prominent scholar N. Davkaraev:

“The bakhshi did not perform these dastans in the ancient written style, but adapted them in accordance with the mentality of the Karakalpak people, introducing certain modifications and sometimes shortening the plot. Almost all dastans were adopted by the bakhshi from the Turkmen bakhshi Suyev, who lived among the Karakalpaks in the 19th century, and from the Uzbek bakhshi of Khorezm, Eshboy bakhshi, performing them in their manner” [11, p.261].

The renowned Karakalpak epic scholar Professor K. Maksetov, discussing the spread of dastans of this category among the Karakalpaks, writes:

“The Karakalpak bakhshi were in constant creative contact with Uzbek and Turkmen bakhshi. The dastan Sayatkhan-Khamra, which was popular among the Uzbeks of Khorezm and the Turkmen living there, existed and was performed based on the master-apprentice tradition of bakhshi who lived and created in the same territory. Having become integrated into the creative practice of the Karakalpak people, it turned into a genuine cultural treasure” [11, pp.290–291].

Like other national versions, the Karakalpak version of the dastan Sayatkhan-Khamra has many variants. Among them are those performed by bakhshi Zhumman Turaev, Minazh Matsapayev, Karajan Kabulov, and Amet Tariykhov, which are currently preserved in the library archives of the KKO Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. The version by Minazh Matsapayev was published in 1985 in Volume XIV of the multi-volume edition Karakalpak Folklore, and the version by Zhumman Turaev in 2011 in Volume XXXVI of the same series. The manuscript versions of

Karajan Kabulov and Amet Tariykhov remain unpublished, while the version of Tengel bakhshi Kamalov is kept in the private archive of K. Maksetov.

Every work of art possesses its own compositional distinctiveness. The structure of folk creations and the system of events differ to some extent in their use of plots and motifs. The span from the beginning of events to the resolution of the main hero's fate unfolds within the work in an interconnected manner.

In the Karakalpak version of the dastan, the narrative begins by defining the setting: "In the city of Ganjikorabag of the Khazar province lived two friends" [6, p.191].

Or: "In ancient times, in the Azerbaijani land, there lived two companions — Oshik Akhmad and Oshik Momut" [7, p.255].

These initial formulas provide us with an idea of the lives of these characters: "All their lives they were filled with feelings of love. Therefore, they were called Oshik Akhmad and Oshik Momut" [7, p.255].

In the Uzbek version of the dastan, Oshiq Ahmad and Oshiq Muhammad, though being close relatives, do not possess any musical talent [14,14]. In the Turkmen version, the word "oshik" is not used; one of them is identified as a padishah (Ahmad) and the other as a vizier (Mahmut) [16,112]. Despite the common prologue in all versions, each displays its own national distinctiveness.

The prologue of the dastan Sayatkhan–Hamra contains the motif of childlessness: "Neither of them had sons nor daughters; they were childless" [7,255]; "They reached the age of forty. However, neither had any children" [6,191]. The story tells of two friends, Oshiq Ahmad and Oshiq Momut, which reflects a typological plot commonly found in many dastans. Childless people, having reached a certain age, begin to think about offspring and turn to divine forces, asking for a child. This motif also appears in several other Karakalpak dastans. Plots based on such motifs demonstrate typological similarities with epic works of world folklore [5,79]. For instance, childless characters appear in the ancient Indian epics Mahabharata and Ramayana [10,16; 12,24], the Oghuz epic Bamsi Beyrek [9,32], and other works of this kind.

The Uzbek version of the dastan narrates: “Both of them were relatives. Their wives were expecting. On the same night, both had children” [14,14]. This cliché is also repeated in the Turkmen version, which states: “One day, Ahmad Khan had a son. The next day, the vizier had a daughter” [16,112]. In this version, the main characters appear as a padishah and a vizier, whereas in the Karakalpak versions they are depicted as close friends. The examples above show that, while the initial formulas of the dastan have a typological character, they also possess distinct national features. In the Karakalpak version, the story focuses on two companions who decide to become in-laws, which determines the epic development of the motif of childlessness.

The prologue of the Karakalpak dastan Sayatkhan–Hamra, like those mentioned above, was formed on the basis of epic experience and rooted in national tradition. For example, the dream motif is consistently preserved in all versions of the dastan, though it appears differently in each. In the Turkmen and Uzbek versions, the episode begins with the merchant Hamra informing others about Sayatkhan [16,112]. In the Turkish variants, the main hero has a dream in which a white-bearded guardian hands him a goblet of wine, saying to Emrah: “Drink this—it is the drink of love. You must fall in love with the daughter of Miroğlu, Selvi” [2,15–20]. This episode, with minor variations, also appears in the Azerbaijani version Oshiq Hujja [3,136–157]. In the Azerbaijani version recorded by A. Akhundov, Amrah, upon seeing the image of Sayat, falls in love with her and sets out to find her [3,158–159]. Overall, the dream motif in these national versions stands out for its typological characteristics.

In dastans, it is traditional for the hero to ask permission from his parents and bid farewell to his loved ones before setting out on a journey. The hero’s safety and success largely depend on the father’s blessing. Despite the objections of his father, mother, and Sarbinoz, Hamra manages to gain their consent [7,256–259]. In general, the plots, motifs, and episodes presented in the opening section of Sayatkhan–Hamra form the foundation for the dastan’s thematic development and the emergence of

actions, reflecting typological features of epic creativity shaped by national worldviews.

The events of the dastan Sayatkhan–Hamra begin with Hamra seeing his beloved in a dream and setting out to find her. This episode highlights the means by which the hero must overcome the obstacles and difficulties that await him on his journey in search of love. The hero mainly faces moral, rather than physical, challenges, and overcoming them serves as a distinctive test of true love.

The beginning of the dastan’s events, along with Hamra’s actions, is closely tied to the role of his father, Oshiq Ahmad. Oshiq Ahmad accompanies his son on the journey to find Sayatkhan. He carefully protects his son and stays by his side throughout, appearing in all versions as a “caring force.”

It should be noted that in the Karakalpak version of the dastan, Oshiq Ahmad’s main goal is not merely his son’s marriage, but rather protecting him from dangers and helping him achieve his mission. For this reason, the reciters of the dastan intentionally chose Oshiq Ahmad as his son’s companion on the journey.

Researcher U. Babadzhanova, who studied the Uzbek version of the dastan, makes a valid observation: “This character plays a key role in setting the events of the dastan in motion. His actions—entering Sayatkhan’s garden, getting stuck naked in the water channel, and being punished by the maids—are presented in a vivid and humorous manner” [4,22].

The meeting of Sayatkhan and Hamra marks a new stage in the development of the dastan’s plot. The lovers, who had seen each other in dreams, faint upon meeting face to face.

However, in the Karakalpak version of Sayatkhan–Hamra, after describing the lovers’ loss of consciousness during their encounter, the performers masterfully depict their inner emotional turmoil [6,211; 7,268]. In the Uzbek and Turkmen versions of the dastan, the following descriptions occur: “Seeing Hamra’s black eyes, Sayatkhan fell unconscious... Hamra stood motionless” [14,34]; “Sayatkhan lost her senses... her consciousness left her... Hamra too... upon seeing Sayatkhan’s face,

stood still, overwhelmed” [16,128]. Such portrayals represent a common typological feature of romantic folk dastans.

From this point of view, romantic dastans of Eastern peoples often include episodes reflecting daily life and express an exceptional beauty that can cause one to lose consciousness. The expression of beauty in dastans is presented equally for both lovers. Indeed, when referring to any dastan, it becomes evident that the beauty of its characters is depicted to the highest degree. Their beauty is portrayed as comparable to—or even surpassing—that of Sayatkhan [16,36].

The stages of formation and development of events forming the structural basis of the dastan incorporate traditional plots and motifs characteristic of folk creativity, reflecting specific transformations and evolution of national features.

The plots, episodes, and motifs that determine the conclusion of events in Sayatkhan–Hamra serve as the final culmination of the work’s content. Sayatkhan’s father, Mamatkhan, is unaware of his daughter’s actions. Upon learning of them from others, he takes measures to stop her. In the Karakalpak version, Mamatkhan himself stands at the center of these events and, leading an army (in some versions accompanied by forty warriors), sets out to pursue his daughter.

In the Uzbek versions recited by Khujamurat Bakhshi and Khudaybergen Bakhshi, similar episodes of confrontation are found. In the lithographed editions published in 1914 and 1964, as Sayat and Hamra approach their homeland, they are overtaken by Sayatkhan’s father, who leads a large army in pursuit. Sayatkhan engages in battle with them and triumphs. Researcher U. Babadzhanova writes: “While Sayat and Hamra appear as ordinary lovers in the oral versions, in this version they immediately attract public attention through their actions, which resemble the heroic imagery typical of epic dastans” [4,33].

In the Turkmen version published in 1960, this episode is presented in a completely different way. Sayatkhan’s father, Mamatkhan, fights against the army of Abdullah Khan. Sayatkhan and Hamra come to his aid, and with their help Mamatkhan defeats his enemy and subsequently gives his blessing to their marriage

[8,3–8]. In the Azerbaijani version, Sayat Khan's father imprisons Amrah, but Sayat frees him [3,136–157]. In Alimjan Akhundov's version, the padishah sentences Amrah to death; however, after his courtiers inform the ruler about Amrah's sincere love, the padishah tests his feelings and eventually pardons him [3,158–159].

This motif is considered a unique national feature of the Uzbek and Karakalpak versions. Specifically, in the Central Asian versions, typological stages are gradually adapted to local conditions.

Although the depiction, development, and resolution of events in the various versions of the dastan are linked to certain episodes, their artistic expression differs. In some Turkmen variants, the motif of Sayat and Hamra's revenge on the robbers who blocked their path—killing them in a cunning way—is preserved [8,128]. In the lithographed Uzbek versions, this motif concludes with Sayat Khan's battle against the robbers and her victory over them [4,31–32].

It is also worth noting that the plots of the Turkmen and Uzbek versions exhibit detailed and complete resolutions. The narrated events reach their full and logical conclusion.

The typological features present in the exposition, development, and resolution of the dastan's plot fully correspond to the national epic worldview of the Karakalpak people and ensure the compositional integrity of the work.

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